

Enhancing German-English Spoken Language Translation Models: A Comprehensive Exploration of Training Strategies and Data Sources

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This paper centers on the translation from German to English, aiming to delve into factors that enhance translation models, specifically those nuances not easily tested using conventional translation tools. To achieve this, various methods were employed, including adjusting training parameters, reorganizing the training data based on complexity and domain, implementing back-translation (English to German), and incorporating texts from diverse domains. Evaluation of these models involves testing on a prepared set and the Tatoeba test set, utilizing BLEU and chrF2 scores as metrics. Additionally, a detailed examination of translation outputs in a sentence level is conducted.

The study is grounded in spoken language, chosen for its representation of everyday language use. Data collection was carried out through the International Workshop on Spoken Language Translation (IWSLT): Offline Speech Translation. Resources for spoken language were curated from various sources, as outlined below, ensuring a representation of linguistic varieties in diverse contexts, domains, and sentence structures—crucial elements for training an effective model.

Dataset	Number of Pairs	Avg. Char./Sent. (DE)	Avg. Char./Sent. (EN)	Avg. Char.
tatoeba-v2022-03-03	322,361	42.35	36.72	39.53
ted_2020	289,373	103.22	96.1	99.66
news-commentary-v16	398,981	161.27	134.33	147.8
ELRC-CORDIS_News	111,275	164.79	142.15	153.47
Total	1,121,990			

The News-commentary and ELRC-CORDIS_News sets encompass spoken news reports, wherein the vocabulary maintains an academic tone, but the style is casual. TED Talks, on the other hand, exhibit a semi-academic vocabulary coupled with a casual style, featuring shorter and less complex sentence structures compared to news reports. The Tatoeba set stands out with the least formal vocabulary and the shortest sentences.

To make sure that the source and target translations align, I use parallel texts. The main pre-processing step is, therefore, to split the parallel file into German and English texts. Other pre-processing steps include decompressing gzip files and converting XML into TXT format. I paste the German and English sentences next to one another in a single file in order to shuffle it without losing the alignment before dividing the combined corpus into training, testing, and evaluation sets with the ratio of 80-10-10 respectively. This resulted in 897,592 sentences in the training set and 112,199 in the testing and the evaluation sets for both languages. After that, I used the training file to create a subword segmentation model and produce the vocab files with word frequencies.

Baseline Model [Model 1]

In the YAML file, I prepared a transformer model training script with the following parameters: RNN_size and word_vec_size of 512, 6 layers, and 8 heads. This model (Model 0) saw a continuous improvement in the accuracy and perplexity scores as the training step progressed. That was an indicator that the training steps could be further increased.

However, in the training log file, I noticed that there were empty lines in the corpus, so I returned to the shuffled file and removed 9,771 empty lines ending up with 1,112,219 lines in total. After the shuffled file was splitted into the train, test, and val files with the same ratio (80-10-10), some empty lines showed up (252, 323, 40, 37, 39, and 37 for train, test, and val files in English and German language respectively.) I

removed them again with different commands (`grep`, `sed`, and `awk`) resulting in 0 empty lines with '^\$' matching inspection; however, after I manually looked at the file, some empty lines still remained meaning the regular expression '^\$' could not detect them. Given these accounted for less than 0.05% of the datasets, I decided to continue with the training to see the translation result leaving this issue to be handled in the following model improvement stage. I sampled the files multiple times to make sure both language files contain the same number of sentences, and most of them were aligned. From these datasets with less empty lines, I created new segmented files and the vocab files with word frequencies. Then, I trained the model again with an increased step from 50k to 400k. The scores finally became stagnant at around step 390k with the accuracy of 87.7 and the perplexity of 6.1.

Training Accuracy and Perplexity Scores of Baseline Model 1

I used the baseline model 1 at step 390k to translate the prepared test set, as well as the Tatoeba test set. I used the Tatoeba development set version 2023-09-26 to create a subword segmentation decoding model for the Tatoeba test set translation with the `word_size` of 10k.

Test Sets	BLEU (Model 1)	chrF2 (Model 1)
Tatoeba/Opus Benchmark	53.1	0.694
Prepared Test Set	0.1	0.128
Tatoeba Test Set	57.5	0.686

The BLEU and chrF2 scores of the translation from the prepared test set is 0.1 and 0.128 respectively while it is 57.5 and 0.686 respectively for the Tatoeba test set. This baseline model already surpasses the Tatoeba/Opus benchmark BLEU score of 53.1 and came close with chrF2 score of 0.694 thanks to its diverse training set. The undetectable empty lines in the prepared test set, however, severely impacted its scores (BLEU of 0.1 and 0.128 for chrF2) because of the screwed alignment.

Despite the empty lines in the training set, Model 1 yielded natural, concise, and grammatically consistent outputs even from a complex and long sentence as shown below. Line 111,208 is an example of native-like translations; however, they may not get a high chrF2 score because they do not match with the reference translation on a character-to-character basis. The same issue can be observed in the first underlined part of line 111,215, where the reference translation of “verfolgt” is “will seek to” while it is “aims to” in the Model 1 translation. In the second underlined sections of line 111,215, Model 1 translates the adjectival phrase “neuer, selektiverer und effektiverer” in a correct pattern as “new, more selective and more effective” instead of “new and more selective and effective” in the reference translation. The last section of line 111215 shows that Model 1 handles complex grammatical dependencies effectively because the noun phrase “Optimierung von Therapien” parallels with the preceding noun phrase “der schnellen Anwendung,” so it should be translated as a noun phrase “the optimisation of therapies” instead of a present participial phrase “optimising therapy.”

- line 111208 src.: Ich bin beim Fernsehen eingeschlafen.
- line 111208 ref.: I fell asleep while I was watching TV.
- line 111208 tgt.: I fell asleep watching TV.
- line 111215 src.: Die Ausschreibung verfolgt die Entwicklung transnationaler innovativer Projekte im Bereich der Onkologie mit dem klaren Ziel der schnellen Anwendung neuer, selektiverer und effektiverer Tools und Strategien zur Prävention, Diagnose und Früherkennung, sowie der Optimierung von Therapien für neoplastische Erkrankungen.
- line 111215 ref.: The call will seek to develop transnational innovative projects in oncology, clearly oriented towards a rapid application of new and more selective and effective tools and strategies for the prevention, diagnosis and early detection, as well as optimising therapy of neoplastic diseases.
- line 111215 tgt.: The call aims to develop transnational innovative projects in the field of oncology with a clear goal of the rapid application of new, more selective and more effective tools and strategies for prevention, diagnosis and early detection, and the optimisation of therapies for neoplastic diseases.

Improved Baseline Model

Model 2

[Layers increased. Dataset with empty lines replaced with TED Talks. Europarl added]

After the investigation, I found the source of the empty lines. They came from the news-commentary-v16 dataset where the news texts were divided into groups separated by empty lines. Therefore, I replaced it with a new dataset, TED Talks 2013. I also added the Europarl dataset in the corpus to make the model more generalizable. When compared to the other datasets, language in Europarl corpus is the most formal and from a different setting, and the sentences are the most complex and the longest, so the Europarl dataset represents a text from a different domain and context, which would help train a more versatile model. This resulted in a 12.82%-larger corpus with 1,265,771 translation pairs (1,012,616 sentences in the training set and 126,577 in the test and validation sets.)

Datasets	Number of Pairs	Avg. Char./Sent. (DE)	Avg. Char./Sent. (EN)	Avg. Char.
tatoeba-v2022-03-03	322,361	42.35	36.72	39.53
ted_2013	142,762	91.77	101.42	96.59
ted_2020	289,373	103.22	96.1	99.66
ELRC-CORDIS_News	111,275	164.79	142.15	153.47
europarl-v10	400,000	170.49	151.48	160.98
Total	1,265,771			

To accommodate a larger and more complex and diverse corpus, in the subword segmentation model training, I adjusted the vocab_size from 70k to 100k, and in the translation model training, I increased the layers from 6 to 8. In addition, because I planned to add a back-translation to the training set to improve the model at a later stage, I trained two models in both translation directions simultaneously. The back-translation (EN-DE) model had a slightly lower performance in terms of accuracy and perplexity than the DE-EN model throughout the training process.

Training Accuracy and Perplexity Scores of Model 2 (DE-EN) and Back-translation (EN-DE)

In the first 400k steps, Model 2 DE-EN reached a peak at step 390k with the accuracy of 89 and the perplexity of 6. Compared to the baseline model 1, Model 2 saw a higher accuracy (87.7 and 89 respectively) yet trained at a slower pace. The increased layers required more computational effort, thus slowing down the training process. I applied Model 2 at step 390k on the prepared and the Tatoeba test sets and measured the translation quality. The scores are as follow:

Model 1 VS Model 2	BLEU (M1)	BLEU (M2)	chrF2 (M1)	chrF2 (M2)
Tatoeba/Opus Benchmark	53.1		0.694	
Prepared Test Set / 390k	0.1	41.8	0.128	0.616
Tatoeba Test Set / 390k	57.5	57.9	0.686	0.671

With a more diverse and complex training set, more layers, and without empty lines, Model 2 at step 390k resulted in a slightly higher BLEU score but a lower chrF2 score on Tatoeba test set when compared to the benchmark (57.9 and 0.671 compared to 53.1 and 0.694 respectively.) In terms of improvement from Model 1, the BLEU score of Model 2 was not much higher (57.9 of Model 2 compared to 57.5 of Model 1) and chrF2 score was lower (0.671 compared to 0.686 respectively,) setting aside the scores of the prepared test set of Model 1, which were messed up with the empty lines. The BLEU and chrF2 scores of Model 2 on the prepared test set were still lower than the benchmark (41.8 and 0.616 compared to 53.1 and 0.694 respectively). In the examination of the Tatoeba test set translation output below (line 23 and 24,) although both Model 1 and 2 struggled to translate numbers, Model 2 outputs with numbers were less readable as they contained many <unk> tokens. Outputs from the prepared test set (line 44 and 60) further revealed that Model 2 at step 390k could not handle low-frequency words like

proper nouns and uppercased words including abbreviations very well. That was an indication of overfitting.

- Tatoeba line 23 ref.: 95 years old! God Save the Queen!
- Tatoeba line 23 M1: Ninety-five years old! God shook the Queen!
- Tatoeba line 23 M2: <unk> _years _old ! _God _Save _the _Q ueen !
- Tatoeba line 24 ref.: The fire killed 85 people.
- Tatoeba line 24 M1: The fire killed 185 people.
- Tatoeba line 24 M2: <unk> _people _died _in _the _fire.
- prepared set line 44 ref.: RECEIVE UPDATES AUTOMATICALLY
- prepared set line 44 M2.: EXAMPLES OF ?? TO ?? EL ??
- prepared set line 60 ref.: Local scientists and organisations in Africa (focused on Mount Cameroon, Fogo in Cape Verde) and Asia (on Merapi in Indonesia, and Kanlaon in Philippines) are closely involved in the risk assessment.
- prepared set line 60 M2.: Clinical scientists and institutions in Africa (?? ons, Cameroon, Cape Verde in the Cape ?? Islands) and Asia (?? ?? : ?? in Indonesia and Kla ?? in the Philippines) are closely involved in the risk assessment.

Consequently, I adjusted the layers down from 8 to 6 and continued the training step to 900k. (I also applied similar settings to Models 3 and 4.) During the training, after a sudden drop due to the adjustments at step 400k, Model 2 still continued improving before leveling off at step 900k with the accuracy of 92.7 and the perplexity of 5.4. The scores of the translation outputs are as follow:

Training Accuracy and Perplexity Scores of Model 2 (DE-EN) and Back-translation (EN-DE)

Model 2 (DE-EN)	BLEU	chrF2
Tatoeba/Opus Benchmark	53.1	0.694
Prepared Test Set / 390k	41.8	0.616
Prepared Test Set / 620k	43.5	0.627
Prepared Test Set / 720k	43.6	0.626
Prepared Test Set / 800k	43.7	0.627
Prepared Test Set / 900k	43.8	0.627
Tatoeba Test Set / 390k	57.9	0.671
Tatoeba Test Set / 620k	60.5	0.696
Tatoeba Test Set / 720k	60.7	0.699
Tatoeba Test Set / 800k	60.6	0.699
Tatoeba Test Set / 900k	60.7	0.700

Tuning the configurations and further training resulted in a vast improvement in BLEU and chrF2 scores. The scores in between the training showed that the model was improving and not overfitting. At step 620k, the chrF2 score of the Tatoeba test set exceeded the benchmark (0.696 and 0.694 respectively.)

Model 3 [Data rearranged]

In this model, I experimented with data arrangement. Like humans, language models are supposed to learn better when the training data is well-arranged and organized. In other words, I hypothesize that the

Training Accuracy and Perplexity Scores of Model 2 and 3

arrangement of data in the training file can impact the efficiency and effectiveness of the model. Grouping sentences from the same domain and context together can help the model focus on specific patterns and characteristics relevant to that domain. To test this hypothesis, I shuffled each 5 dataset separately and put one next to another to build a corpus. I layered a simpler set

before a more complex one assuming Tatoeba being the least complex followed by TED Talks and ELRC CORDIS news report respectively while the most complex dataset is Europarl based on an average number of characters in a sentence in the model 2 dataset table. The data arrangement is illustrated in the chart above on the left.

Based on the graph above on the right, the training line of Model 3 fluctuated, reflecting the unblended training data. This data arrangement factor in Model 3 did not render its accuracy and perplexity scores higher than those of Model 2, so I stopped the training and moved on to improve Model 4.

Model 4 [Back-translation added, Data preprocessed, RNN and Vector Size Adjusted]

In this improvement stage, I picked up from Model 2 and added a back-translation (English to German). I resorted to a monolingual source, OpenSubtitles, to minimize noise from translations. OpenSubtitles contains subtitles from films, so it represents an authentic form of spoken language. In the preprocessing step, I removed the subtitle-related characters “-” and “” from OpenSubtitles and included only the lines with more than 8 numbers of fields (NF>=8.) I removed duplicates, excluded any lines with more than 8 symbols, shuffled the dataset, and cut only 303,784 lines from OpenSubtitles, accounting for 30% of the training set (1,012,616 lines.) As a result, the Model 4 training set has 1,316,400 lines.

Model 2 (EN-DE)	BLEU	chrF2
Prepared Test Set / 600k	36.6	0.597
Prepared Test Set / 700k	36.8	0.598
Prepared Test Set / 800k	36.8	0.598
Prepared Test Set / 900k	36.8	0.598
Tatoeba Test Set / 600k	59.6	0.716
Tatoeba Test Set / 700k	60.1	0.721
Tatoeba Test Set / 800k	60.4	0.823
Tatoeba Test Set / 900k	60.7	0.725

Based on EN-DE translation scores in the left table, the best performing Model 2 (EN-DE) is the one at step 800k, so it was employed to translate the subtitles. Then, I consolidated a parallel DE_EN set and appended it to the training set before shuffling and splitting it to German and English train sets. In the first 20k steps, I compared two configurative versions, RNN and vector size of 256 and 512, before continuing the training of the better version to step 900k. To catch up with a larger training set and tackle the less-frequent words identified in Model 2, the vocab size was increased from 70k to 180k (when the least frequent words in the vocabulary file have the occurrence of 1-2 times.) The scores of Model 4 translations are shown in the table below.

Training Accuracy and Perplexity Scores of Model 2 and Model 4

Model 4 (DE-EN)	BLEU	chrF2
RNN 256, Vector Size 256		
Prepared Test Set / 20k	32.5	0.556
Tatoeba Test Set / 20k	39.6	0.547
RNN 512, Vector Size 512		
Prepared Test Set / 20k	33.5	0.563
Tatoeba Test Set / 20k	41.0	0.557

Despite an almost double training time, Model 4 with the 512 configuration showed a better BLEU score than the 256 version on the Tatoeba test set (41.0 and 39.6 respectively) and only a slightly higher chrF2 score on the prepared test set (0.563 and 0.556 respectively.) Therefore, I kept training

the 512 version to step 900k and recorded the training performance as shown in the left graph (compared with the one of Model 2.) Model 4 reached a peak at step 890k with the accuracy of 86.2 and the perplexity of 6.6 compared to 92.7 and 5.4 respectively of Model 2. The translation score comparison of Model 1, 2, and 4 at different training steps is in the table below.

Model 1 / Model 2 / Model 4	BLEU (M1)	BLEU (M2)	BLEU (M4)	chrF2 (M1)	chrF2 (M2)	chrF2 (M4)
Tatoeba/Opus Benchmark		53.1			0.694	
Prepared Test Set / 390k	0.1	41.8	38.2	0.128	0.616	0.593
Prepared Test Set / 620k	N/A	43.5	38.9*	N/A	0.627	0.596*
Prepared Test Set / 720k	N/A	43.6	39.0	N/A	0.626	0.596

Prepared Test Set / 800k	N/A	43.7	39.1**	N/A	0.627	0.596**
Prepared Test Set / 900k	N/A	43.8	39.2	N/A	0.627	0.597
Tatoeba Test Set / 390k	57.5	57.9	51.3	0.686	0.671	0.625
Tatoeba Test Set / 620k	N/A	60.5	52.1*	N/A	0.696	0.630*
Tatoeba Test Set / 720k	N/A	60.7	52.5	N/A	0.699	0.632
Tatoeba Test Set / 800k	N/A	60.6	52.7**	N/A	0.699	0.633**
Tatoeba Test Set / 900k	N/A	60.7	52.8	N/A	0.700	0.634

*measured at step 640k due to a technical problem

**measured at step 810k due to a technical problem

Based on the training performance and the translation scores, it turned out that Model 4 with back-translation did not demonstrate an improvement from Model 2. Even though the translation noise was partially avoided by selecting a monolingual source instead of the translated corpus, some noise and inaccuracies still remained after translating the monolingual texts. In other words, the added back-translation was of an inferior quality to the rest of the training set, which was a parallel text. This resulted in the degradation of Model 4 performance.

Examining translated texts from Model 2 and 4 at different steps, while the texts from both models have different styles in terms of word choice, Model 2 exhibits a superior capability in offering accurate sense of words and authentic lexicons. Take for example the phrase “kan ... keine Zeit erübrigen” in sentence 65 in the prepared test set translated as “can’t spare any time” by Google Translate. The output of Model 2 and 4 at step 390k are as follow.

- src: Tom hat auf der Arbeit sehr viel zu tun und kann bis übernächste Woche keine Zeit erübrigen.
- ref: Tom's been very busy at work and can't get any time off until the week after next.
- M2: Tom has a lot of work to do and can't spare time until week.
- M4: Tom is very busy at work and can't turn off time until last week.

Model 2 translation “can’t spare time” is the closest to Google Translate output while Model 4 translation “can’t turn off time” sounds unnatural. Further training made Model 2 more fluent in translating the phrase. Model 2 step 810k and 900k translated the source text as “can’t afford to spend a lot of time” as shown below.

- M2 620k: Tom has a lot to do at work and can't spare time until next week.
- M2 720k: Tom's work is very busy and can't spend a lot of time till last week.
- M2 810k: Tom has a lot of work to do and can't afford to spend a lot of time until next week.
- M2 900k: Tom has a lot to do at work and can't afford to spend a lot of time until next week.

Being less authentic, Model 4 output of the phrase became more similar to the reference translation as the training continued, developing from “can’t buy time off” at step 640k, 720k, and 810k to “can’t take time off” at step 900k.

- M4 640k: Tom is very busy at work and can't buy time off till ?! a week.
- M4 720k: Tom is very busy at work and can't buy time off till friday week.
- M4 810k: Tom is very busy at work and can't buy time off till ?! a week.
- M4 900k: Tom is very busy at work and can't take time off till friday week.

Line 95 below confirms the observation that Model 2 and 4 give the translations in different styles: Model 2 translates “bitten um” as “ask for” in all steps while it is “request” for Model 4 steps 390k and 640k. As for the phrase “eine Streichung eines gemeinsamen Entschließungsantrags,” Model 2 outputs are more natural, concise, and consistent, being “the removal of a joint resolution” in the last three comparison steps. Model 4 outputs, on the other hand, are less accurate translating “gemeinsamen Entschließungsantrags” as “a common text” at step 720k and “a joint text” at other steps instead of “a joint resolution.”

- src: Heute Früh bat der Vorsitzende der Fraktion der Progressiven Allianz der Sozialisten & Demokraten im Europäischen Parlament um eine Streichung eines gemeinsamen Entschließungsantrags von der Tagesordnung.
- ref: This morning, the President of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament asked for a motion for a joint resolution to be withdrawn from the agenda.
- M2 390k: This morning, the chairman of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament asked for the deletion of a joint motion for a resolution from the agenda.
- M2 620k: This morning, the chairman of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament asked for the removal of a joint motion for a resolution from the agenda.
- M2 720k: This morning, the chairman of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament asked for the removal of a joint resolution from the agenda.
- M2 800k: This morning, the chairman of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament asked for the removal of a joint resolution from the agenda.

- M2 900k: This morning, the chairman of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament asked for the removal of a joint resolution from the agenda.
- M4 390k: This morning, the Chairman of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament requested the deletion of a joint text with a view to removing from the agenda.
- M4 640k: This morning, the Chairman of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament requested that a joint text item be removed from the agenda.
- M4 720k: This morning, the chairman of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament asked for a common text item to be withdrawn from the agenda.
- M4 810k: This morning, the Chairman of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament asked for a joint text item to be withdrawn from the agenda.
- M4 900k: This morning, the chairman of the Group of the Progressive Alliance of Socialists and Democrats in the European Parliament asked for a joint text from the agenda.

Conclusions and Discussions

The final project explores German to English translation models, aiming to enhance their performance through various methods such as adjusting training parameters, modifying training data, and back-translation. Collected from the International Workshop on Spoken Language Translation (IWSLT), the dataset focuses on spoken language to represent everyday language use.

The initial model, referred to as Model 1, showed continuous improvement, reaching an accuracy of 87.7 and perplexity of 6.1. Despite issues with undetected empty lines affecting scores, Model 1 surpassed the Tatoeba/Opus benchmark in BLEU (53.1) and approached its chrF2 score (0.694). However, empty line issues impacted BLEU and chrF2 scores for the prepared test set. Model 2, an improved baseline model, addressed empty line issues by incorporating TED Talks and Europarl datasets. With adjustments in layers, it achieved an accuracy of 92.7 and perplexity of 5.4 at 900k steps. While BLEU scores slightly improved, chrF2 scores fluctuated, and overfitting issues were observed with numbers and low-frequency words. In the data rearrangement model (Model 3), the hypothesis that well-arranged data enhances model efficiency was tested. However, Model 3 did not outperform Model 2, prompting the need for further improvements. The back-translation model (Model 4) introduced back-translation using OpenSubtitles for English to German, with adjustments to RNN and vector sizes. Despite a larger dataset, Model 4 did not outperform Model 2 either. Inconsistencies and noise from back-translation affected translation quality.

In conclusion, Model 2, with a diverse dataset and careful adjustments, performed better than subsequent models. Further fine-tuning, especially with back-translation, requires meticulous handling of noise and source selection. The study provides insights into the intricate process of refining translation models, considering factors like dataset composition, model architecture, and preprocessing steps.

One caveat in this project involved the inclusion of Tatoeba parallel texts in the corpus, which could harm the reliability of the measurement. Upon examination, it was revealed that 16.51% of the data overlapped with the Tatoeba benchmark test set. Assuming an even distribution of sentences in Tatoeba across the training, testing, and evaluation sets with an 80-10-10 ratio, approximately 13.20% remained exclusively in the training set. This highlights a significant challenge when narrowing the focus to spoken language, necessitating the procurement of texts from diverse sources with various domains and contexts to ensure dataset diversity. Through this capstone project, I gained insights into the complexity of machine translation, particularly when narrowing the scope to spoken language. The exploration led me to realize the importance of diversifying datasets from multiple sources to capture a broader context. Throughout the data collection process, I navigated websites such as <https://iwslt.org/>, <https://opus.nlpl.eu/>, and <https://github.com/Helsinki-NLP>, which house extensive language data. This experience has equipped me with valuable resources for future projects and explorations, extending beyond machine translation into various disciplines.

Repository: https://github.com/aminomewza/machine_translation/blob/273ab1c2f5211fce6143a1bbc537b0392583b5de/datasets2.zip